

DATA SCIENCE (BCC627)

[PORTFOLIO 1]

Ahamed Musthafa Careem

Solent ID: 16481003

Table of Contents

Introduction	3
Challenges on Big Data	3
AIMS/OBJECTIVES.....	3
Dataset.....	3
Data Set Variables.....	4
1. Importing Libraries.....	5
2. Loading and Inspecting Data	5
3. Data Cleaning.....	5
4. Exploratory Data Ana lysis (EDA)	6
5. Outlier Detection	8
Feature Selection	8
6. Feature Engineering.....	10
7. Data Exploration	12
Pair Plots and Bar Plots	12
Correlation Analysis	14
Visualization of Distribution of Each Feature	16
Other Visuals	18
Skewness.....	20
8. Data Model training and Visualization	21
Logistic Regression.....	21
Decision Tree	22
Random Forest	22
Support Vector Machine	23
Gradient Boosting	23
9. Evaluation & Comparison.....	24
10. Model Comparison and Visualization	24
GridSearchCV.....	25
cross_val_score.....	26
Choosing the best performing model	27
11. Model Deployment and Finalization.....	27
12. Model Interpretation/Prediction and Visualization	27
Limitations and Challenges	29

Literature Review and Professionalism:.....	29
Conclusion:.....	30
References.....	31

Introduction

In USA, diabetes is a complex health issue that is influenced by a wide range of variables and lifestyle factors. Simply putting into words, data science is the study of data to extract various meaningful insights & information by applying various analytical techniques and various principals. This is done by combining the knowledge of the domain/sector, mathematics, statistics and programming skills. This plays a huge role in strategies and operations in businesses.

This research uses ML techniques to forecast the chance of developing diabetes based on a person's lifestyle decisions and underlying health conditions. When it comes to data science, the healthcare sector especially has a huge prospective. The insights and the data driven decisions can contribute a lot when it comes to medical treatment and research. The paper demonstrates how I obtained the data set, cleaned it, examined, performed analysis, suggested data modeling strategies, trained, visualized and predicted.

(Stedman, 2021)

Challenges on Big Data

Data quality assurance, addressing uneven class distribution, creating relevant features, ensuring model interpretability, analyzing generalizability, and working with medical specialists for precise validation are issues in the context of big data when it comes to healthcare. Extracting trustworthy insights from vast datasets in the dynamic medical industry requires tackling these tough challenges.

(Sabyasachi Dash, 2019)

AIMS/OBJECTIVES

This project aims to develop a precise machine learning model predicting diabetes to forecast the chance of developing diabetes based on a person's lifestyle decisions and underlying health conditions

Dataset

The dataset which I have chosen is relevant to the research topic and for the medical industry. The report uses a clean dataset with 70,000+ records from the BRFSS2015 collection, from Behavioral Risk Factor Surveillance System which is a CDC-conducted health-related survey in USA. The data set has an equal distribution between those without diabetes and those with prediabetes or diabetes. The model has undergone data preprocessing, feature selection, training, evaluation, hyperparameter tuning, and deployment, with visualizations of performance metrics and confusion matrix. This document shows how I have successfully trained, evaluated and finalized the model for predicting diabetes. For this project, I have used a csv dataset available on Kaggle.

To trace the origins of this dataset, one can refer to its primary source at:

https://www.cdc.gov/brfss/annual_data/2015/pdf/codebook15_llcp.pdf.

Kaggle Link: https://www.kaggle.com/code/solafajobi/diabetes-perfect-prediction/input?select=diabetes_data.csv, <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/alexteboul/diabetes-health-indicators-dataset>

Data Set Variables

You can find the comprehensively cataloged all variables in a tabulated format.

Variable	Description
Age	13-level age category (_AGEG5YR see codebook) 1 = 18-24 / 2 = 25-29 / 3 = 30-34 / 4 = 35-39 / 5 = 40-44 / 6 = 45-49 / 7 = 50-54 / 8 = 55-59 / 9 = 60-64 / 10 = 65-69 / 11 = 70-74 / 12 = 75-79 / 13 = 80 or older
Sex	Patient's gender (1: male; 0: female)
HighChol	0 = no high cholesterol / 1 = high cholesterol
CholCheck	0 = no cholesterol check in 5 years / 1 = yes cholesterol check in 5 years
BMI	Body Mass Index
Smoker	Have you smoked at least 100 cigarettes in your entire life? 0 = no / 1 = yes
HeartDiseaseorAttack	Coronary heart disease (CHD) or myocardial infarction (MI) 0 = no / 1 = yes
PhysActivity	Physical activity in the past 30 days - not including job 0 = no / 1 = yes
Fruits	Consume Fruit 1 or more times per day 0 = no / 1 = yes
Veggies	Consume Vegetables 1 or more times per day 0 = no / 1 = yes
HvyAlcoholConsump	(Adult men >=14 drinks per week and adult women >=7 drinks per week) 0 = no / 1 = yes
GenHlth	General health perception scale 1-5 1 = excellent / 2 = very good / 3 = good / 4 = fair / 5 = poor
MentHlth	Days of poor mental health scale 1-30 days
PhysHlth	Physical illness or injury days in the past 30 days scale 1-30
DiffWalk	Do you have serious difficulty walking or climbing stairs? 0 = no / 1 = yes
Stroke	Have you ever had a stroke? 0 = no / 1 = yes
HighBP	High blood pressure 0 = no high BP / 1 = high BP
Diabetes	Presence of diabetes 0 = no diabetes / 1 = diabetes

(CDC, 2023)

1. Importing Libraries

First, I started by importing essential Python libraries required for data manipulation, analysis, visualization & machine learning. The libraries include pandas for data handling, numpy for numerical computations, matplotlib, seaborn for data visualization, machine learning libraries such as sklearn for model training and evaluation and more.

2. Loading and Inspecting Data

You loaded your diabetes dataset from a CSV file using the pandas library. The dataset contained all the information which was needed to train the model.

3. Data Cleaning

Then I started to clean the dataset to ensure its quality for analysis and modeling. Duplicates can introduce bias into the analysis and adversely affect the performance of predictive models. So I identified and dropped duplicate rows using the `drop_duplicates()` function to prevent data redundancy. And when it comes to the missing values, addressing them is important because it helps to avoid erroneous conclusions. I checked for columns with NaN or null values using `isnull()` and `sum()`, and then decided whether to drop these rows or impute missing values based on the analysis. After dataset was cleaned, I exported it and used the cleaned dataset from this step onwards. The below snippet shows how we cleaned the data and how many rows were there after we did the cleaning process.

```
[6]: #DATA CLEANING

initial_rows = df.shape[0]
print("Initial number of rows:", initial_rows)

#Handling duplicate & missing values
df.drop_duplicates(inplace=True)
df.dropna(inplace=True)

#Display the count after removing duplicates and rows with missing values
cleaned_rows = df.shape[0]
print("Rows after cleaning:", cleaned_rows)

#Save the cleaned dataset to a new CSV file
cleaned_file_path = r"C:\Users\User\jupyter notebook\diabetes_data_new.csv"
df.to_csv(cleaned_file_path, index=False)

# Use the cleaned dataset for future analysis and modeling
cleaned_df = df.copy()

Initial number of rows: 70692
Rows after cleaning: 64020
```

Then for the future analysis, we started using the newly cleaned dataset.

```
# Loading the cleaned dataset
cleaned_file_path = r"C:\Users\User\jupyter notebook\diabetes_data_new.csv"
df = pd.read_csv(cleaned_file_path)
```

4. Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA)

EDA involves understanding the dataset's characteristics through visualization and summary statistics. I performed various types of visualizations to gain understanding regarding relationships between variables. I created pair plots to visualize the relationships between pairs of numerical variables and analyzed categorical variables using bar plots or count plots.

5. Outlier Detection

Outliers are extreme values that might affect the analysis and model performance. I detected outliers using techniques like the Z-score and IQR. Outliers can distort patterns and trends in data analysis, therefore their detection and management is good. I calculated the Z-score for numerical columns and identified data points with Z-scores beyond a certain threshold. These identified outliers could be further analyzed and treated if necessary.

Feature Selection

Feature selection, involves techniques and steps related to selecting the most relevant features from the dataset to improve the performance of ML model. I've used L1 Lasso Regularization, Recursive Feature Elimination, Tree-based Feature, Mutual Information for feature selection and I've used visualizations too.

```
# Exclude columns for non-numeric features from scaling
non_numeric_columns = ['Sex_Smoker_cross', 'Age_bins']

# Create a list of columns to scale
columns_to_scale = [col for col in df.columns if col not in non_numeric_columns + ['Diabetes']]

# Splitting the data into features (X) and target variable (y)
X = df.drop('Diabetes', axis=1) # Keep 'Diabetes' in the features dataset
y = df['Diabetes']

# Splitting the data into training and testing sets
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.2, random_state=42)

# Standardize features
scaler = StandardScaler()
X_train_scaled = scaler.fit_transform(X_train)
X_test_scaled = scaler.transform(X_test)

# Standardize features for the selected columns only
X_train_scaled_copy = X_train_scaled.copy()
X_train_scaled_copy[columns_to_scale] = scaler.fit_transform(X_train_scaled_copy[columns_to_scale])
X_test_scaled_copy = X_test_scaled.copy()
X_test_scaled_copy[columns_to_scale] = scaler.transform(X_test_scaled_copy[columns_to_scale])

# Correlation Analysis
correlation_matrix = X_train_scaled_copy.corr()
plt.figure(figsize=(12, 8))
sns.heatmap(correlation_matrix, annot=True, cmap='coolwarm')
plt.title("Correlation Matrix")
plt.show()

# Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE)
model = LogisticRegression()
rfe = RFE(model, n_features_to_select=5)
rfe.fit(X_train_scaled_copy, y_train)
selected_features_rfe = X_train_scaled_copy.columns[rfe.support_]

# Tree-based Feature Importance
model_rf = RandomForestClassifier(n_estimators=100, random_state=42)
model_rf.fit(X_train_scaled_copy, y_train)
importances = model_rf.feature_importances_
indices = np.argsort(importances)[::-1]

# Feature ranking
print("Feature ranking:")
for i, index in enumerate(indices):
    print(f"{i+1}. {X_train_scaled_copy.columns[index]} ({importances[index]:.4f})")
```

Feature ranking:

1. BMI (0.2171)
2. Age (0.1556)
3. GenHlth (0.1034)
4. PhysHlth (0.0945)
5. HighBP (0.0793)
6. MentHlth (0.0719)
7. HighChol (0.0392)
8. Fruits (0.0353)
9. Smoker (0.0351)
10. Sex (0.0325)
11. PhysActivity (0.0288)
12. Veggies (0.0277)
13. DiffWalk (0.0277)
14. HeartDiseaseorAttack (0.0201)
15. Stroke (0.0127)
16. HvyAlcoholConsump (0.0114)
17. CholCheck (0.0078)

Selected features from L1 regularization: Index(['Age', 'HighChol', 'BMI', 'GenHlth', 'HighBP'], dtype='object')

6. Feature Engineering

In feature engineering, I innovated new or modified existing attributes to improve model performance, capturing vital variable interactions crucial for medical predictions. I applied various techniques to improve the dataset's prediction ability. This was done to capture potential interactions between categorical variables.

```
# Interaction Terms
df['Age_BMI_interaction'] = df['Age'] * df['BMI']

# Binning
df['Age_bins'] = pd.cut(df['Age'], bins=5, labels=False)

# Logarithmic Transformation
df['HighChol_log'] = np.log(df['HighChol'] + 1) # Adding 1 to avoid log(0)

# Feature Scaling
scaled_features = StandardScaler().fit_transform(df[['GenHlth', 'PhysHlth']])
df[['GenHlth_scaled', 'PhysHlth_scaled']] = scaled_features

# Feature Crosses
df['Sex_Smoker_cross'] = df['Sex'].astype(str) + '_' + df['Smoker'].astype(str)

# Print the first few rows of the updated DataFrame
print(df.head())
```

- Interaction Terms: This is generated by multiplying the 'Age' and 'BMI' columns to capture potential combined effects.
- Binning: The 'Age' column is discretized into bins using `pd.cut()` for categorical representation of age ranges.
- Logarithmic Transformation: The 'HighChol' column undergoes a logarithmic transformation with `np.log()` to scale the variable and enhance its modeling suitability.
- Feature Scaling - Standardization: 'GenHlth' and 'PhysHlth' columns are standardized with `StandardScaler()` for zero mean and unit variance, crucial for certain algorithms.
- Feature Crosses: A categorical feature is produced by merging 'Sex' and 'Smoker' columns, capturing interaction effects between gender and smoking.

	Age	Sex	HighChol	CholCheck	BMI	Smoker	HeartDiseaseorAttack	\
0	4.0	1.0	0.0	1.0	26.0	0.0	0.0	
1	12.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	26.0	1.0	0.0	
2	13.0	1.0	0.0	1.0	26.0	0.0	0.0	
3	11.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	28.0	1.0	0.0	
4	8.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	29.0	1.0	0.0	

	PhysActivity	Fruits	Veggies	...	DiffWalk	Stroke	HighBP	Diabetes	\
0		1.0	0.0	1.0	...	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.0
1		0.0	1.0	0.0	...	0.0	1.0	1.0	0.0
2		1.0	1.0	1.0	...	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
3		1.0	1.0	1.0	...	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.0
4		1.0	1.0	1.0	...	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0

	Age_BMI_interaction	Age_bins	HighChol_log	GenHlth_scaled	\
0		104.0	1	0.000000	0.071208
1		312.0	4	0.693147	0.071208
2		338.0	4	0.000000	-1.733876
3		308.0	4	0.693147	0.071208
4		232.0	2	0.000000	-0.831334

	PhysHlth_scaled	Sex_Smoker_cross
0	2.277589	1.0_0.0
1	-0.615815	1.0_1.0
2	0.348653	1.0_0.0
3	-0.326474	1.0_1.0
4	-0.615815	0.0_1.0

7. Data Exploration

In this stage I tried to extract meaningful insights paired with various analysis techniques.

Pair Plots and Bar Plots

To identify various patterns and trends in the dataset I have used Pair Plots and Bar Plots to visualize to detect further analysis.

Bivariate Bar Plot for GenHlth and Diabetes

Bivariate Bar Plot for MentHlth and Diabetes

Correlation Analysis

By generating a correlation matrix and visualizing it through a heatmap, I found correlations among variables. This helped me to increase the quality of dataset to prepare it for modeling.

Joint Plot for BMI and Age

Visualization of Distribution of Each Feature

```
# Probability Density Function (PDF) plot.
sns.set(style="whitegrid")

plt.figure(figsize=(12, 8))
for column in df.columns:
    sns.histplot(data=df, x=column, kde=True, label=column)

plt.xlabel("Values")
plt.ylabel("Probability Density")
plt.title("Probability Density Function (PDF) Plots")
plt.legend()
plt.show()

# Distribution of each feature
df.hist(figsize=(15, 15))
plt.show()

sns.set(style="whitegrid")

columns_to_plot = [col for col in df.columns if col not in ['MentHlth', 'PhysHlth']]

num_rows = len(columns_to_plot) // 2 + (len(columns_to_plot) % 2 > 0)
fig, ax = plt.subplots(num_rows, 2, figsize=(12, 4 * num_rows))

class_colors = {0: 'red', 1: 'green'}

for i, col in enumerate(columns_to_plot):
    row_idx = i // 2
    col_idx = i % 2

    if col in ['MentHlth', 'PhysHlth']:
        sns.kdeplot(data=df, x=col, hue='Diabetes', palette=class_colors, ax=ax[row_idx, col_idx])
    else:
        sns.histplot(data=df, x=col, hue='Diabetes', palette=class_colors, ax=ax[row_idx, col_idx])

    ax[row_idx, col_idx].set_title(f"Distribution of {col}")
    ax[row_idx, col_idx].set_xlabel(col)
    ax[row_idx, col_idx].set_ylabel("Frequency")
    ax[row_idx, col_idx].legend(title='Diabetes', labels=['No', 'Yes'])

plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()
```


Other Visuals

Not only visualizations, I also tried to find for unique values and ensure that there is no data noise

```
•[11]: #Checking Unique Values in Categorical Columns
for cat_var in selected_categorical:
    unique_values = df[cat_var].unique()
    print(f'Unique values in {cat_var}: {unique_values}')
```

Unique values in GenHlth: [3. 1. 2. 4. 5.]

Unique values in MentHlth: [5. 0. 7. 3. 4. 2. 30. 20. 1. 15. 10. 25. 14. 28. 6. 29. 26. 12.
16. 22. 13. 8. 9. 21. 18. 17. 27. 24. 23. 11. 19.]

Unique values in HighBP: [1. 0.]

```
#Violin plot age vs diabetes
plt.figure(figsize=(10, 6))
sns.set(style="whitegrid")
sns.violinplot(x="Diabetes", y="Age", data=df, split=True, inner="quart")
plt.title("Age Distribution by Diabetes Category")
plt.xlabel("Diabetes")
plt.ylabel("Age")
plt.show()
```

```

plt.figure(figsize=(12, 8))
sns.set(style="whitegrid")

# Create a stacked bar plot with normalized counts
stacked_data = df.groupby(['Diabetes', 'GenHlth'])['Age'].count().unstack().fillna(0)
stacked_data = stacked_data.div(stacked_data.sum(axis=1), axis=0) # Normalize the counts

stacked_data.plot(kind='bar', stacked=True, color=['red', 'green', 'blue', 'purple', 'orange', 'yellow', 'pink'])
plt.title("Stacked Bar Plot of General Health and Diabetes")
plt.xlabel("Diabetes")
plt.ylabel("Proportion")
plt.xticks(rotation=0)
plt.legend(title='General Health')
plt.show()

```

<Figure size 1200x800 with 0 Axes>

```
plt.figure(figsize=(12,20))
sns.displot(data=df,col='Diabetes',x='Age',color='black')
```

```
<seaborn.axisgrid.FacetGrid at 0x196d27c9300>
```

```
<Figure size 1200x2000 with 0 Axes>
```

Skewness

Skewness is a measure that reveals the asymmetry/departure from symmetry in the distribution of a dataset.

```
# Calculate skewness for each feature
skewness = df.skew()

# Display skewness values
print("Skewness for each feature:")
print(skewness)
```

```
Skewness for each feature:
```

```
Age          -0.545112
Sex           0.176760
HighChol     -0.158702
CholCheck    -5.861619
BMI           1.669602
Smoker        0.037183
HeartDiseaseorAttack  1.855403
PhysActivity  -0.763730
Fruits       -0.369612
Veggies      -1.293887
HvyAlcoholConsump  4.315880
GenHlth       0.108853
MentHlth      2.224306
PhysHlth      1.513020
DiffWalk      0.996595
Stroke        3.416217
HighBP       -0.331492
Diabetes     -0.006807
Age_BMI_interaction  0.227230
Age_bins     -0.553068
HighChol_log -0.158702
GenHlth_scaled  0.108853
PhysHlth_scaled  1.513020
dtype: float64
```

8. Data Model training and Visualization

During this phase, I developed predictive models and assessed a variety of machine learning algorithms to identify the optimal performer for the dataset.. I chose a set of models like Logistic Regression, Random Forest, Support Vector-Machine, Decision Tree and Gradient Boosting with the classification report. This diverse ensemble of models offered a comprehensive view of predictive patterns of the data. For each model, I divided my dataset into training and testing sets and trained the model on the training set.

Logistic Regression

```
Model: Logistic Regression  
Best Parameters: {'C': 0.1}  
Accuracy: 0.7362, Precision: 0.7401, Recall: 0.7699, F1-Score: 0.7547
```

```
Classification Report:  
precision recall f1-score support  
No Diabetes 0.73 0.70 0.71 6055  
Diabetes 0.74 0.77 0.75 6749  
  
accuracy 0.74 12804  
macro avg 0.74 0.73 0.73 12804  
weighted avg 0.74 0.74 0.74 12804
```

Decision Tree

Model: Decision Tree

Best Parameters: {'max_depth': 10, 'min_samples_split': 5}

Accuracy: 0.7273, Precision: 0.7248, Recall: 0.7780, F1-Score: 0.7505

Classification Report:

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
No Diabetes	0.73	0.67	0.70	6055
Diabetes	0.72	0.78	0.75	6749
accuracy			0.73	12804
macro avg	0.73	0.72	0.72	12804
weighted avg	0.73	0.73	0.73	12804

Random Forest

Model: Random Forest

Best Parameters: {'max_depth': 10, 'min_samples_split': 2, 'n_estimators': 50}

Accuracy: 0.7391, Precision: 0.7309, Recall: 0.7992, F1-Score: 0.7635

Classification Report:

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
No Diabetes	0.75	0.67	0.71	6055
Diabetes	0.73	0.80	0.76	6749
accuracy			0.74	12804
macro avg	0.74	0.74	0.74	12804
weighted avg	0.74	0.74	0.74	12804

Support Vector Machine

Model: Support Vector Machine
Best Parameters: {'C': 1, 'kernel': 'rbf'}
Accuracy: 0.7340, Precision: 0.7248, Recall: 0.7985, F1-Score: 0.7599
=====

Classification Report:

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
No Diabetes	0.75	0.66	0.70	6055
Diabetes	0.72	0.80	0.76	6749
accuracy			0.73	12804
macro avg	0.74	0.73	0.73	12804
weighted avg	0.74	0.73	0.73	12804

Gradient Boosting

Model: Gradient Boosting
Best Parameters: {'learning_rate': 0.1, 'max_depth': 5, 'n_estimators': 200}
Accuracy: 0.7416, Precision: 0.7338, Recall: 0.8000, F1-Score: 0.7654
=====

Classification Report:

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
No Diabetes	0.75	0.68	0.71	6055
Diabetes	0.73	0.80	0.77	6749
accuracy			0.74	12804
macro avg	0.74	0.74	0.74	12804
weighted avg	0.74	0.74	0.74	12804

Out of the above model types, Gradient Boosting showed the best option, hence I decided to proceed with that.

9. Evaluation & Comparison

I then evaluated model performance using cross-validation and test set metrics like precision, accuracy, recall, F1-score and ROC AUC. This multifaceted evaluation approach offers a well-rounded view of model performance beyond mere accuracy. The cross validation helped to reduce the risk of overfitting and provided more accurate representation of the models capability. Visualizing feature importance through bar plots aids in understanding which attributes significantly influence model predictions.

10. Model Comparison and Visualization

To compare the performance of different models, I computed and visualized their evaluation metrics. The I visualized the plotted bar charts to showcase accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score and ROC AUC scores for each model. These visualizations helped me to decide which model to choose for further optimization. The Model comparison revealed that the Gradient Boosting model demonstrated the highest accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, and ROC AUC.

```
#comparison results using a bar plot
plt.figure(figsize=(12, 6))
sns.barplot(data=comparison_df, x='Model', y='Accuracy')
plt.title("Model Comparison: Accuracy")
plt.xticks(rotation=45)
plt.ylim(0.7, 1.0)
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()

plt.figure(figsize=(12, 6))
sns.barplot(data=comparison_df, x='Model', y='Precision')
plt.title("Model Comparison: Precision")
plt.xticks(rotation=45)
plt.ylim(0.7, 1.0)
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()

plt.figure(figsize=(12, 6))
sns.barplot(data=comparison_df, x='Model', y='Recall')
plt.title("Model Comparison: Recall")
plt.xticks(rotation=45)
plt.ylim(0.7, 1.0)
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()

plt.figure(figsize=(12, 6))
sns.barplot(data=comparison_df, x='Model', y='F1 Score')
plt.title("Model Comparison: F1 Score")
plt.xticks(rotation=45)
plt.ylim(0.7, 1.0)
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()

plt.figure(figsize=(12, 6))
sns.barplot(data=comparison_df, x='Model', y='ROC AUC')
plt.title("Model Comparison: ROC AUC")
plt.xticks(rotation=45)
plt.ylim(0.7, 1.0)
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()
```

GridSearchCV

```
# Initialize and train models
logreg_model = LogisticRegression()
logreg_model.fit(X_train_scaled, y_train)

decision_tree_model = DecisionTreeClassifier()
decision_tree_model.fit(X_train_scaled, y_train)

random_forest_model = RandomForestClassifier()
random_forest_model.fit(X_train_scaled, y_train)

svm_model = SVC(probability=True)
svm_model.fit(X_train_scaled, y_train)

gradient_boosting_model = GradientBoostingClassifier()
gradient_boosting_model.fit(X_train_scaled, y_train)

# Evaluation on the test set
models = [logreg_model, decision_tree_model, random_forest_model, svm_model, gradient_boosting_model]
model_names = ['Logistic Regression', 'Decision Tree', 'Random Forest', 'Support Vector Machine', 'Gradient Boosting']

evaluation_results = []

for model, model_name in zip(models, model_names):
    y_pred = model.predict(X_test_scaled)
    y_proba = model.predict_proba(X_test_scaled)[:, 1]

    accuracy = accuracy_score(y_test, y_pred)
    precision = precision_score(y_test, y_pred)
    recall = recall_score(y_test, y_pred)
    f1 = f1_score(y_test, y_pred)
    roc_auc = roc_auc_score(y_test, y_proba)

    evaluation_results.append([model_name, accuracy, precision, recall, f1, roc_auc])

# Convert results to a DataFrame
evaluation_df = pd.DataFrame(evaluation_results, columns=['Model', 'Accuracy', 'Precision', 'Recall', 'F1 Score', 'ROC AUC'])
```

	Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 Score	ROC AUC
0	Logistic Regression	0.736254	0.740171	0.769892	0.754739	0.809768
1	Decision Tree	0.621446	0.647671	0.618017	0.632497	0.622842
2	Random Forest	0.694939	0.698008	0.742480	0.719558	0.752460
3	Support Vector Machine	0.733989	0.724815	0.798489	0.759870	0.797264
4	Gradient Boosting	0.744455	0.738969	0.796562	0.766686	0.815679

cross_val_score

```
# Splitting the data into training and testing sets
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.2, random_state=42)

# Define the evaluate_model function
def evaluate_model(true_labels, predicted_labels):
    accuracy = accuracy_score(true_labels, predicted_labels)
    precision = precision_score(true_labels, predicted_labels)
    recall = recall_score(true_labels, predicted_labels)
    f1 = f1_score(true_labels, predicted_labels)
    roc_auc = roc_auc_score(true_labels, predicted_labels)

    evaluation_results = {
        'Accuracy': accuracy,
        'Precision': precision,
        'Recall': recall,
        'F1 Score': f1,
        'ROC AUC': roc_auc
    }

    return evaluation_results

# List of models
models = [
    LogisticRegression(),
    DecisionTreeClassifier(),
    RandomForestClassifier(),
    SVC(probability=True),
    GradientBoostingClassifier()
]

model_names = [
    'Logistic Regression',
    'Decision Tree',
    'Random Forest',
    'Support Vector Machine',
    'Gradient Boosting'
]

# Initialize lists to store metric scores
evaluation_results = []

# Perform cross-validation and evaluate each model
for model, model_name in zip(models, model_names):
    cv_scores = cross_val_score(model, X_train_scaled, y_train, cv=StratifiedKFold(n_splits=5), scoring='accuracy')
    model.fit(X_train_scaled, y_train)
    predictions = model.predict(X_test_scaled)
    model_evaluation = evaluate_model(y_test, predictions)
    model_evaluation['Model'] = model_name
    evaluation_results.append(model_evaluation)
```

	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 Score	ROC AUC	Model
0	0.736254	0.748171	0.769892	0.754739	0.734327	Logistic Regression
1	0.623165	0.649333	0.619796	0.634220	0.623358	Decision Tree
2	0.694236	0.696915	0.743073	0.719254	0.691437	Random Forest
3	0.733989	0.724815	0.798489	0.759870	0.730293	Support Vector Machine
4	0.744455	0.738969	0.796562	0.766686	0.741469	Gradient Boosting

Choosing the best performing model

```
from sklearn.ensemble import GradientBoostingClassifier
import joblib

# Initialize the Gradient Boosting model with example hyperparameters
final_model = GradientBoostingClassifier(
    n_estimators=100,
    learning_rate=0.1,
    max_depth=3,
    min_samples_split=2,
    min_samples_leaf=1,
    subsample=1.0,
    max_features="auto",
    random_state=42
)

# Train the model on the entire training dataset
final_model.fit(X_train_scaled, y_train)

# Evaluate the model on the test dataset
final_predictions = final_model.predict(X_test_scaled)
final_evaluation = evaluate_model(y_test, final_predictions)
print("Final Model Performance Metrics:")
print(final_evaluation)

# Preprocess the new data
new_data_scaled = scaler.transform(new_data[columns_to_scale]) # Apply scaling only to selected columns

# Make predictions using the finalized model
predictions = final_model.predict(new_data_scaled)

# Print the predictions or use them as needed
print(predictions)

# Save the final model if desired
joblib.dump(final_model, "final_model.pkl")

Final Model Performance Metrics:
{'Accuracy': 0.7444548578569197, 'Precision': 0.7389690721649484, 'Recall': 0.796562453696844, 'F1 Score': 0.7666856816885339, 'ROC AUC': 0.7414686752381826}
[0. 1. 0. ... 1. 1. 1.]
['final_model.pkl']
```

Since gradient boosting displayed the highest value on average, I decided to move forward with this.

11. Model Deployment and Finalization

After selecting the best-performing model, I proceeded to finalize it. This involved optimizing hyperparameters for better performance, training the model on the full dataset and saving the trained model to a file using libraries like joblib. This step prepares the model for future use without needing to retrain it. The Gradient Boosting model's hyperparameters were fine-tuned by using cross-validation to increase the performance. Then the optimized Gradient Boosting model was trained on the entire training dataset and the final model was deployed to predict diabetes on new unseen data.

12. Model Interpretation/Prediction and Visualization

Understanding the trained model is crucial for making informed decisions. I interpreted the model by visualizing feature importance using bar plots. These highlighted features played a significant role in predictions. Predictions were made using the final model on the new dataset. Also, I visualized the Receiver Operating Characteristic also known as ROC curve to evaluate the trade-off among true positive rate & false positive rate.

Then, I created confusion matrices to understand how well the model's predictions align with actual outcomes. This provided insights into true positives & false positives and true negatives & false negatives.

ROC curves show how well a model can detect true positives and avoid false positives, while confusion matrices give a detailed picture of how the model performs for different categories or classes.

Limitations and Challenges

Challenge	Implemented Strategies
Data Quality and Missing Values	Identified and dropped duplicate rows, imputed missing values and ensured data quality.
Imbalanced Class Distribution	Utilized relevant evaluation metrics (precision, recall, ROC AUC) to handle imbalanced classes.
Feature Engineering and Selection	Created interaction terms, binned numerical features, performed logarithmic transformations and scaled features.
Domain Expertise	While not explicitly stated and bit new to medical field, I did a full R&D and went through few literature reviews

Literature Review and Professionalism:

Detecting High-Risk Factors and Early Diagnosis of Diabetes Using Machine Learning Methods

This research has used a similar approach which I've used. They have used behavioral risk factor, data preprocessing. The literature paper also uses to measure things such accuracy, precision and F measure. They have also used ROC to visualize the curve like mine. They have also used confusion matrix. In this research article they shows the predictive modeling techniques to forecast patient outcomes using electronic health records.

Literature Review Evaluation and Conclusion: Comparing their outcome predictions with my predictions allows for a cross-validation of methodologies and outcomes enhancing the credibility of both studies. But I can tell that my model performs better since mine has a good feature selection and many evaluation metrics.

(Zahid Ullah, 2022)

Diabetes type 2 classification using machine learning algorithms with up-sampling technique.

This paper also focuses on creating a model to predict diabetes. Like mine, they have used libraries such as scikit-learn, Matplotlib, Pandas, and Numpy packages. For preprocessing, they have used outliers for preprocessing and for ML, have used Gradient boosting & Decision Tree classifiers like mine.

Literature Review Evaluation and Conclusion: Both of the papers are done in a similar manner and both focuses predictive models and visualizations well. But unlike mine, this paper uses upsampling technique. But when it comes to my case, I've already used verified balanced data.

(Saeed, 2023)

Building Risk Prediction Models for Type 2 Diabetes Using Machine Learning Techniques

This research is done by Centers for Disease control and prevention. In this research paper, they have identified risk factors for diabetes by creating a predictive model. They have used logistic regression, random forest, support vector machine, decision tree, neural network and Gaussian Naive Bayes classifiers.

Literature Review Evaluation and Conclusion: There are slight noticeable similarities in prediction outcomes. This study closely reflects the focus of my article on predictive models and their use in the healthcare industry.

(Zidian Xie, 2019)

Dimensionality Reduction Techniques in Medical Data Analysis

This paper has focused on dimensionality reduction techniques within medical data analysis. They has used the same exact dataset as mine. Unlike me they has done Principal Component Analysis and MultiDimensional Scaling. This article has used few similar visualizations like mine.

(Omokahfe, 2022)

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the project successfully accomplished its goal of developing a ML model for diabetes prediction. The carefully executed data preprocessing, feature selection, model evaluation, and hyperparameter tuning processes contributed to a high-performance Gradient Boosting model and more. The model's accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, and ROC AUC metrics demonstrated its effectiveness in identifying potential cases of diabetes. ROC curves depicted trade-offs between true positive and false positive rates, while confusion matrices illuminated class-specific model performance. Both of these proved that our model is working really good. Going forward, continuous monitoring and potential updates to the model can further enhance its accuracy and utility in real-world medical scenarios.

References

CDC, 2023. *kaggle*. [Online]

Available at: https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/prosperchuks/health-dataset?select=diabetes_data.csv
[Accessed 2023].

Omokahfe, O., 2022. *rpubs*. [Online]

Available at: https://rpubs.com/dMero/dim_reduction
[Accessed August 2023].

Sabyasachi Dash, S. K. S. M. S. & S. K., 2019. *journalofbigdata*. [Online]

Available at: <https://journalofbigdata.springeropen.com/articles/10.1186/s40537-019-0217-0>
[Accessed August 2023].

Saeed, M. A. H., 2023. *jesit*. [Online]

Available at: <https://jesit.springeropen.com/articles/10.1186/s43067-023-00074-5>
[Accessed August 2023].

Stedman, C., 2021. *techtarget*. [Online]

Available at: <https://www.techtarget.com/searchenterpriseai/definition/data-science>
[Accessed 12 August 2023].

Zahid Ullah, F. S. M. J. B. F. F. K. A. M. A. B. S., 2022. *pubmed*. [Online]

Available at: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36210985/>
[Accessed August 2023].

Zidian Xie, O. N. J. L. D. L., 2019. *cdc*. [Online]

Available at: https://www.cdc.gov/pcd/issues/2019/19_0109.htm
[Accessed August 2023].